

HogDSim - A within-farm modeling framework for infectious diseases of swine

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ABSTRACT

Effective prevention of pathogen transmission through biosecurity practices is vital for maintaining pig health and productivity. This study presents HogDSim, a novel within-farm model for farrow-to-finish pig farms. The model incorporates epidemiological scenarios that account for farm structure and pathogen spread via both animal and farmer movement. Farmer mobility is tracked using Bluetooth[®]-enabled personal beacons and detection points, allowing high-resolution monitoring of human-mediated transmission routes. We demonstrate the model using swine influenza A virus (swIAV) as a case study in a single farrow-to-finish farm. Transmission parameters were calibrated via Approximate Bayesian Computation Sequential Monte Carlo across scenarios with varying data availability, where synthetic infection data were generated from literature-based swIAV parameters. Additionally, we offer a concise demonstration of the model's application in evaluating biosecurity measures. HogDSim is a modular framework for simulating within-farm disease dynamics. It integrates epidemiological processes, animal and farmer movements, an auxiliary transmission route, and modules for detection and ABC-SMC calibration. Using swIAV as a case study, we show that calibration from fattening-area observations can recover main transmission pathways, although auxiliary-route parameters remain difficult to identify under sparse surveillance. While demonstrated on swIAV, the framework is adaptable to diverse pathogens, biosecurity strategies, and farm configurations, supporting reproducible scenario comparison.

1. Introduction

Pig production is a significant sector in animal husbandry, primarily focused on raising pigs for pork. A farrow-to-finish farm is a pig production system that encompasses all stages of pig growth, from breeding and gestation to farrowing (birth), nursery, and finally, growing the pigs to market weight. This type of operation is designed to maximize efficiency and productivity. However, pig production is not without its challenges, particularly in terms of disease management. Diseases in pig populations can lead to significant economic losses due to decreased productivity, increased mortality, and the costs associated with treatment and prevention measures [12]. In addition, some common swine diseases such as swine influenza viruses are zoonotic pathogens capable of infecting humans, particularly through direct contact with pigs. Although human-to-human transmission of swIAV is limited, the emergence of variant strains such as H1N1v and H3N2v underscores the im-

portance of surveillance and control measures [36,43]. These viruses pose a public health risk and highlight the need for integrated disease control strategies to protect both animal and human health within the food production system [36].

The transmission of pathogens within a swine farm is influenced by several factors, including the farm's organizational structure, physical layout, and the segregation of animals into specific groups, such as gestation, farrowing, and fattening units [6,30,41]. Pathogens can spread among pigs via multiple pathways, such as direct contact between animals, indirect transmission through contaminated surfaces or fomites, and airborne routes [21]. The relative importance of these transmission routes and, therefore, the effectiveness of corresponding biosecurity measures, varies depending on the pathogen involved [2,19,34,44]. Implementation of robust biosecurity measures, including disinfection protocols and restricted access to different farm zones, is crucial for disease control [6,19]. A recent technological innovation supporting such efforts

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is Biorisk®, developed by Animal Data Analytics (formerly PigCHAMP Pro-Europa). Biorisk® utilizes detection points and Bluetooth®-enabled personal beacons to monitor and manage the movement of individuals in a farm [6].

While biosecurity measures are crucial in controlling the spread of infectious pathogens, their effectiveness is often limited by practical, logistic, and economic constraints [48]. The implementation of these measures at scale can be challenging, with success depending on factors such as compliance, environmental conditions, and pathogen characteristics. Furthermore, the dynamic nature of disease transmission necessitates continuous monitoring and regular adjustments to control strategies, demands that can be resource-intensive. To help address these challenges, simulation models offer a valuable tool for predicting disease dynamics, evaluating control scenarios, and optimizing intervention strategies without the need for extensive and time-consuming field studies [15]. Simulation models are a common tool to assess the possible effectiveness of measures in complex farming systems when long-term field studies are not feasible [2]. Moreover, they provide a structured and replicable framework for testing the effectiveness of interventions in complex systems, allowing researchers to explore a wide range of conditions and interactions that would be difficult to isolate in real-world settings [45].

Stochastic simulation models have been used to study within-farm transmission dynamics, with a particular focus on individual pigs and management groups [2,7,30,50]. These models estimate the probability of infection and the reproduction number based on contact between susceptible and infectious pigs [7,49], thereby providing insight into how management practices influence pathogen spread. However, many of these models ignore the physical and organizational structure of swine farms, which usually consist of multiple buildings and rooms within buildings that house animals at different stages of the production process [41]. Accounting for this structural complexity is essential for developing effective biosecurity strategies [17,39,52]. For example, Lurette et al. [30] developed a stochastic model to simulate the dynamics of *Salmonella* spread within a farrow-to-finish pig herd, emphasizing the role of environmental contamination and management practices in the prevalence of infection among pigs at slaughter [30]. Another model, developed by Etbaigha et al. [20], analyzed the dynamics of swIAV infection in a farrow-to-finish farm. It explores reinfection at the farm level and evaluates the effectiveness of control strategies using a deterministic SEIR model. Although both studies considered the different production stages in a farrow-to-finish farm, they did not explicitly incorporate the movement of persons within the farm, which is an important factor in pathogen transmission [17,39]. In both models, transmission between production areas is represented by a general indirect transmission rate [20,30], which does not distinguish between infections resulting from observable movements of persons and those arising from other indirect transmission pathways such as transfer via contaminated fomites.

We introduce HogDSim, a hybrid stochastic model that integrates agent-based detail with compartmental efficiency to simulate disease spread within farrow-to-finish farms. Unlike previous models, HogDSim explicitly accounts for both animal and farmer movements, critical drivers of pathogen persistence, enabling realistic evaluation of biosecurity strategies [17,39].

The primary purpose of HogDSim is to simulate disease dynamics at a granular level in order to evaluate the effectiveness of various on-farm biosecurity practices and control strategies. By doing so, the model supports the development of targeted interventions to mitigate pathogen transmission and safeguard animal health and welfare.

HogDSim is built using the Epidemiological Multi-Level Simulation Framework (Emulsion) [37] and parameterized through Approximate Bayesian Computation with Sequential Monte Carlo simulation (ABC-SMC) [35,46].

To demonstrate HogDSim's capabilities, we apply the framework to a swine influenza A virus (swIAV) infection scenario. The model simulates the full farrow-to-finish farm, including all production areas, transfers, and interactions. For calibration, however, we considered differ-

ent subsets of these simulated outputs as synthetic "observed" data to mimic varying levels of surveillance. These scenarios range from constrained settings, where only fattening-area observations at pen level are assumed available, to broader cases that incorporate aggregated infection counts across age groups or full-farm infection records. We show that (i) the framework can be calibrated even from fattening-area-only observations to recover the main transmission signatures underlying the synthetic swIAV outbreak, and (ii) some parameters (notably the auxiliary-route parameter) remain weakly identifiable under sparse surveillance, an important consideration for the design of monitoring programs and the interpretation of parameter estimates.

2. Methodology

The model tracks individual animals based on attributes such as age, sex, weight, parity (for sows), and their location within the farm (i.e., production area and pen). A production area, in HogDSim, refers to a distinct housing unit within the farm, such as the farrowing, nursery, or fattening sections (i.e., barn sections). Pathogen spread is simulated within this population through horizontal transmission within and between different pens in the same area. Vertical transmission is possible when infected pregnant sows pass the pathogen to their offspring. Transmission between areas can occur via three main pathways: movement of persons, transfer of infected animals, and unidentified routes such as airborne transmission. The model also allows for the introduction of a pathogen from external sources into any area.

2.1. Model description

2.1.1. State variables and scales

The farrow-to-finish swine farm model consists of five production stages: non-gestating, gestating, farrowing, nursery, and fattening areas. Usually, pig farms have designated *areas* for housing pigs in the same production stage, each with its characteristics in terms of herd size, age, and weight of pigs, and the duration of stay of the pig in the area. In addition, each pig is assigned an epidemiological state: susceptible, latently infected, infectious, recovered, or maternally immune.

Individual states. Each pig is characterized by a set of states: sex, parity, production stage, and weight. Sex is a fixed state (i.e., male and female). Only females are raised, and gilts (young female pigs that have not been bred yet) are essential for herd replacement. Parity, age, and weight are dynamic states. Parity reflects reproductive history, with four states: P_0 for nulliparous pigs, i.e. gilts, P_1 for primiparous sows, P_2 for sows with two litters, and P_3 for sows with more than two litters. Production stage indicates where the pig is housed within the system: J_{nb} for newborn piglets and F for the farrowing sows in the farrowing area, J_n for the weaned piglets in the nursery, J_f for growing pigs in the fattening area, A for non-gestating gilts/sows in the non-gestating area, and G for the gestating pigs in the gestation area. Transitions between production stages are determined by age, weight, and gestation status. For piglets and growing pigs (J_{nb} , J_n , and J_f), transitions are primarily based on age and weight. Each pig of potential transition age (see Table 1) is randomly assigned a weight based on a normal distribution that reflects typical values for the given age. Only pigs meeting the minimum weight threshold progress to the next stage; others remain in the area until their assigned weight exceeds the threshold. When the number of non-gestating sows (A) drops below a preset level, gilts J_n are recruited from the nursery, assigned parity P_0 , and moved to A . Upon insemination, sows and gilts A are relocated to the gestation area while assigned the gestating stage G . Shortly before farrowing, they transition to the farrowing area in stage F , and their parity increases by one.

Epidemiological states. The model includes five epidemiological states: susceptible (S), exposed (E), infectious (I), recovered (R), and maternally immune (M). The state M accounts for temporary immunity provided by maternal antibodies, which piglets acquire through colostrum

Table 1
Model parameters and values used in the swIAV application of HogDSim.

Parameter	Definition	swIAV Value ^a	Reference
β_{int}	transmission rate within an area	17.01	Cador et al. [11]
β_{ext}	transmission rate from other areas due to farmer movement	9.87	Cador et al. [11]
β_{pen}	transmission rate from neighboring pens if present	9.87	Cador et al. [11]
β_{aux}	transmission rate from other routes	$\frac{\beta_{int}}{178}$	Reynolds et al. [42]
ρ	recovery rate	$\frac{1}{6.1}$	Cador et al. [11]
ν	vertical transmission rate	0.1	Assumed
μ	base mortality rate	0.001	Assumed
μ_I	mortality rate from the disease	0	Li and Robertson [28]
τ_{ip}	latency period	$\mathcal{U}\left[\frac{0.5}{7}, \frac{5}{7}\right]^d$	Rose et al. [43]
τ_w	time required before weaning newborn piglets	3	Main et al. [32]
τ_n	time required in the nursery area	6–8	Blavi et al. [8]
τ_f	time required in the finishing area	17–18	Blavi et al. [8]
τ_m	length of time maternal immunity is active	$\tau_w + \tau_n$	Martínez-Boixaderas et al. [33]
λ_g	conception rate of gilts	0.5	Assumed
λ_s	conception rate of sows	0.6	Assumed
α_a	age of gilts and sows	24–32	Belkova and Rozkot [4]
ν_{pha}	number of piglets born alive	$\mathcal{N}(13.1, 1.06^2)^c$	Koketsu et al. [26]
ν_w	weight of piglets at weaning	$\mathcal{N}(6.34, 0.7^2)^c$	Pierozan et al. [38]
γ_w	minimum weight required for piglets at weaning	5.5	Camp Montoro et al. [13]
ν_f	weight of pigs before transfer at the finishing area	$\mathcal{N}(30, 5^2)^c$	Pierozan et al. [38]
ω_f	minimum weight required before transfer at the finishing area	24	Camp Montoro et al. [13]
p_{enc}	probability of encounter with an external vector	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)^d$	Assumed
p_{inf}	probability that the external vector is infected	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)^d$	Assumed
p_{trans}	probability of transmission from an infected external vector	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1)^d$	Assumed
p_{biosec}	probability of success of the external biosecurity measure	BetaPERT(a, b, c) ^b	Assumed

^a The unit used for time is weeks while rates are per week. Weights are in kilograms. These values are used for the case study using the swine influenza A virus.

^b The values a, b, c are the pessimistic, most-likely, and optimistic estimates of p_{biosec} , respectively [27].

^c Normally distributed.

^d Uniformly distributed.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the MSEIR model applied to a farrow-to-finish farm. The MSEIR model is applied to each production area. Solid arrows show standard transitions between epidemiological states: maternally immune (M), susceptible (S), exposed (E), infectious (I), and recovered (R). Dashed arrows ($R \rightarrow S$, $M \rightarrow E$) denote optional, disease-specific transitions. Dotted lines indicate mortality, and dash-dot lines represent births.

from sows that have previously been infected or vaccinated. Transitions between states are governed by the parameters: force of infection, length of the latency period, length of the infectious period, and waning of maternal immunity. The model is flexible, additional transitions such as M to E (infection of maternally immune pigs) and R to S (waning of acquired immunity) can be included depending on the disease. Fig. 1 illustrates the MSEIR epidemiological state diagram applied to each production area. Solid arrows represent standard transitions ($M \rightarrow S \rightarrow E \rightarrow I \rightarrow R$), dashed arrows indicate optional transitions (e.g., waning immunity), dotted lines show mortality, and dash-dot lines represent births. This diagram provides the conceptual basis for within-area disease dynamics.

2.1.2. Process overview and scheduling

The proposed farrow-to-finish model simulates the disease transmission within a farm over a designated time frame. The algorithm begins by setting the temporal scale, start date, and end date, followed by the

initialization of population and model parameters for each production area. The simulation proceeds in a time-stepped loop until the terminal time is reached. At each time step, the aggregate force of infection is calculated by invoking subsidiary algorithms. Subsequently, the model updates the within-farm infection dynamics, incorporates possible external introductions, and manages animal movements as necessary. Throughout the simulation, relevant summary statistics are recorded to monitor disease progression, including the states of individual pigs or fattening pens. The following section presents a summary of the model algorithm (Algorithm 1).

To capture the dynamics of pathogen transmission within the farm, the model considers multiple routes of transmission: (1) direct transmission from infected pigs within the same production area, (2) infection from pigs transferred from other areas, and (3) farmer-mediated transmission between areas. Fig. 2 depicts the movement structure within the farrow-to-finish farm. Solid lines indicate animal transfers between production areas, dashed lines represent farmer movements,

Algorithm 1 The within-farm farrow-to-finish model.

- 1: **Input:** Initial populations, model parameters, and farmer movement data
- 2: **Output:** Number of infections per unit time over a specific period
- 3: Define time scale, start date, and end date
- 4: Initialize the population for each area in a farrow-to-finish farm
- 5: Initialize area assignment: place nongestating gilts/sows in the nongestating area, gestating gilts/sows in the gestating area, farrowing sows and newborn pigs in the farrowing area, weaned piglets to the nursery, and growers to the fattening area
- 6: Initialize the age of individuals based on the age requirement
- 7: Initialize variables and model parameters
- 8: Implement Algorithm 3: Calculate the duration of stay of all farmers in each area and record the farmer's route based on farmer mobility data per unit time*
- 9: Set start date to 0 and terminal time T (end date minus start date)
- 10: **while** current time $t < T$ **do**
- 11: Compute overall force of infection (call Algorithms 2, 4, and 5)*
- 12: Implement Algorithm 6: within-farm infection*
- 13: implement Algorithm 8: auxiliary transmission route*
- 14: Implement Algorithm 9: infection from outside source*
- 15: Implement Algorithm 7: move animals if necessary*
- 16: Record relevant summary statistics
- 17: **end while**

* See Supplementary material.

Fig. 2. Animal and farmer movements in the farrow-to-finish model. Solid lines represent animal movements between production areas. Dashed lines indicate farmer movements. Dotted lines show potential auxiliary pathways relevant to certain diseases but not captured by direct animal or farmer movement.

and dotted lines illustrate auxiliary pathways (e.g., airborne or fomites). This figure highlights the multi-route transmission structure incorporated in HogDSim. When pigs in a production area are further subdivided into pens, an additional route is considered: (4) transmission from infected neighboring pens. Pathogen transmission may also occur in utero depending on the nature of the disease (i.e., vertical transmission). Infected or exposed farrowing sows can transmit the infection to piglets in the womb, while recovered sows may provide maternally derived immunity to their offspring through colostrum. Finally, the model includes an auxiliary transmission route that may result in newly infected individuals. This process is similar to the maternally immune compartment (M), where it represents the dissemination of disease not covered by the routes mentioned above (see Section 2.1.6).

The overall per time-step probability of transmission to a pig during a time step is:

$$P_{\text{transmission}} = 1 - e^{-\Gamma} \quad (1)$$

$$\Gamma = \begin{cases} \gamma_{\text{int}} + \gamma_{\text{pen}} + \gamma_{\text{ext}} + \gamma_{\text{aux}}, & \text{if divided into pens} \\ \gamma_{\text{int}} + \gamma_{\text{ext}} + \gamma_{\text{aux}}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the aggregated force of infection, γ_{int} represents the infection rate per unit of time within a given area, γ_{pen} denotes the infection rate per unit of time from adjacent pens, and γ_{ext} the infection rate per unit of time from other areas due to farmer movement, and γ_{aux} accounts for the infection rate per unit of time from other areas via an auxiliary route. Each of these rates is described in detail below.

2.1.3. Farmer movement and pathogen transmission

Farmers routinely move between different areas of a farrow-to-finish farm multiple times per unit of time, and these movements can contribute to pathogen transmission [6,22]. In the model, the force of infection γ_{ext_i} from farmer movements to a production area i is dependent on the frequency of farmer entries into area i , and the duration of the farmer's stay in previously visited areas. These factors are represented by the number of infected pigs I_j , the population size N_j of the farmer f_j 's previous location j , and the normalized duration of the farmer's stay d_{f_j} at location j . However, the available farmer mobility dataset includes only timestamps of entry, not the exact duration spent in each location. Consequently, the model approximated the duration of stay at the previous location j by calculating the time difference between the entry into area i and the most recent prior entry into area j . This computed value is subsequently normalized according to the time intervals utilized within the simulation framework. Thus,

$$\gamma_{\text{ext}_i} = \beta_{\text{ext}} \cdot \sum_{\forall f_j} d_{f_j} \left(\frac{I_j}{N_j} \right) \quad (3)$$

where β_{ext} is the disease-specific transmission parameter from farmer movement.

2.1.4. Animal movement and internal transmission

The movement of animals among various production areas within a farm is critical for the propagation of internal pathogen transmission [20,24]. Swine are regularly transferred between distinct areas, for example, weaning piglets from sows or moving nursery pigs to fattening areas. These movements alter the prevalence of infected and exposed pigs within the recipient area. Hence, the internal force of infection γ_{int_i} is given by

$$\gamma_{\text{int}_i} = \beta_{\text{int}} \cdot \frac{I_i}{N_i} \quad (4)$$

where β_{int} is the internal transmission parameter in a production area, and I_i and N_i are the number of infected and total population area i , respectively.

2.1.5. Neighboring pen transmission

Compartmentalization of a production area into pens adds another layer of disease dynamics [7,49]. Transmission of pathogens from infected swine in adjacent pens can result in the infection of pigs in neighboring pens, but it is also a deterrent since direct contact is limited to individuals in the same pen. The force of infection γ_{pen_i} from a neighboring pen j to a focal pen i is computed as

$$\gamma_{\text{pen}_i} = \beta_{\text{pen}} \sum_{\forall j} \frac{I_j}{N_j} \quad (5)$$

where β_{pen} is the transmission parameter between neighboring pens, I_j is the number of infected pigs in the neighboring pen j , and N_j is the total population of the neighboring pen j . When pens are aligned in a row, the first and last pens each have one neighboring pen, whereas the pens between them have two neighbors.

2.1.6. Auxiliary pathways of transmission

Many infectious diseases have multiple potential transmission routes beyond via farmers or infected animals [19,21,30]. Therefore, it is imperative to also consider other potential transmission pathways between areas, including airborne transmission, via fomites, vector-borne transmission, and environmental contamination [19,21,30]. To address this, the model includes an auxiliary pathway, representing alternative routes of pathogen exposure, not explicitly captured by the main modeled mechanisms. The auxiliary route aggregates residual transmission pathways such as airborne spread between rooms, fomites, pest-mediated transfer, and occasional visitors into a single parameter. This design captures indirect risks without overcomplicating the model structure.

The force of infection from the auxiliary pathway, represented by γ_{aux_i} , is calculated for a focal production area i . This computation is based on the infection forces exerted by areas other than i , under the assumption that transmission through the auxiliary pathway can occur between any pair of locations. This rate is derived from the cumulative infection pressure exerted by the other production areas j . Considering the quantity of infected pigs I_j , and the population N_j at j , we derive

$$\gamma_{aux_i} = \beta_{aux} \cdot \sum_{\forall j \neq i} \frac{I_j}{N_j} \quad (6)$$

where β_{aux} is the transmission parameter for the auxiliary pathway of transmission.

2.1.7. External disease introduction from outside the farm

Beyond the internal dynamics of pathogen transmission, the model also incorporates the potential introduction of pathogens from external sources. While this model primarily focuses on the within-farm dynamics of swine pathogens, it is essential to consider external infection pathways to accurately capture the full scope of disease dynamics within a farm and to provide robust biosecurity recommendations.

In the proposed model, all production areas of the farm are considered susceptible to pathogen introduction from external sources, particularly those introduced via pest and vermin (e.g., rodents) acting as mechanical vectors, contaminated supplies, and visitors. This vulnerability is quantified by a probability P_{out} , which denotes the likelihood of disease introduction from external sources per unit of time for each susceptible individual. This probability is influenced by several factors, including the efficacy of biosecurity measures implemented p_{biosec} , the frequency of potential contacts with infected vectors n , the likelihood of the vector being infected p_{inf} , the probability of a successful encounter p_{enc} , and the probability of pathogen transmission after a successful encounter p_{trans} . Consequently, $P_{out} = p_{enc} \cdot p_{inf} \cdot p_{trans} \cdot (1 - p_{biosec})$.

By incorporating these external transmission pathways, the model captures the complex dynamics of pathogen transmission within a swine farm and enables the evaluation of biosecurity measures in reducing the risk of both disease introduction and spread.

2.1.8. Implementation of biosecurity measures

To test the effectiveness of biosecurity measures, specific modifications are made to selected model algorithms. External biosecurity is already incorporated through the probability of success p_{biosec} (see Section 2.1.7). To incorporate within-farm biosecurity measures, Algorithms 3 and 7 can be modified as follows:

- Removal of risky movements (Modify algorithm 3): Identify and remove farmer's risky movements based on the study of Bernaerd et al. [6]. Suppose moving from area i to area j is defined as risky, set the duration of stay to 0.
- Removal of infectious animal before movement (Modified algorithm 7): Before moving an individual i , test if infectious (I). If i is I , remove it from the area, and no movement is made. If the testing procedure is not 100% sensitive, say 90%, then at most 90% of infectious I individuals that are ready to move are removed. This procedure can also include exposed animals E if required.

2.2. Model implementation

The model is implemented in Emulsion version 1.2rc5 [37]. Since the Emulsion version 1.2rc5 used in this model does not intrinsically process meta-population interaction that defines the dynamics between production stages, a Python add-on code was developed to cover this interaction in the model via farmer and animal movement (see Code availability for the online repository).

2.3. Parameterization and model calibration

A comprehensive evaluation of biosecurity measures requires the utilization of a parameterized model [1,6,19]. This study focuses on the HogDSim framework and its capacity for parameterization and calibration against data. To demonstrate this, we generate synthetic outbreak data from known parameter sets and evaluate whether key transmission parameters can be recovered with an ABC-SMC calibration workflow [35,46]. Implementation and calibration details are provided in the following subsections. Algorithmic details are provided in the Supplementary material.

2.3.1. Parameter estimation

The parameter estimation was performed by leveraging High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources to address the computational demands associated with executing the model multiple times and implementing the ABC-SMC method. Given the complexity of the stochastic model environment, in which likelihood functions are intractable to compute directly, we have employed Approximate Bayesian Computation (ABC) to infer the posterior distribution of the parameters. Specifically, we have employed the Sequential Monte Carlo (SMC) simulation with ABC, which utilizes sequential refinements of estimates and is more efficient in high-dimensional parameter spaces.

To calibrate the ABC-SMC model, it is necessary to define a set of summary statistics capable of capturing the key features of the observed data. These summary statistics are subsequently used to compare the model outputs. To quantify the similarity between simulated and observed statistics, we employ the adaptive Manhattan distance [40]. This distance is based on the L_1 norm, which sums the absolute differences between corresponding summary statistics. In contrast to the Euclidean (L_2) distance, the Manhattan formulation is less sensitive to the influence of outliers, thereby providing a more robust measure of discrepancy. The adaptive component further improves performance by rescaling each statistic according to its variability within the current particle population (typically using the median absolute deviation). This ensures that statistics measured on different scales, or with different levels of dispersion, contribute comparably to the overall distance. By updating these weights iteratively at each SMC step, the algorithm dynamically emphasizes the most informative statistics as inference progresses, enhancing both the precision and efficiency of parameter estimation. The adaptive distance can be represented as follows:

$$d(s, s_{obs}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \left| \frac{s_i - s_{obs,i}}{\sigma_i} \right|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (7)$$

where s and s_{obs} are the summary statistics of the simulated and observed data, respectively, σ_i are the adaptive weights derived from the variability of each statistic and updated at every iteration, and $p = 1$ corresponds to the Manhattan distance.

We assigned a uniform prior distribution for these sets of beta parameters with ranges $\beta_{int} = [0, 20]$, $\beta_{ext} = [0, 15]$, $\beta_{pen} = [0, 15]$, and $\beta_{aux} = [0, 1]$ per week. We will use a weekly time step with this swIAV case study, with all other units including rates, expressed on a per-week basis. The time step can be adjusted within the HogDSim framework if needed.

Following the aforementioned setup, we applied ABC-SMC using the Python package pyABC. The specific parameters used were as follows:

the number of particles accepted was set to 100 to optimize efficiency, the distance used was adaptive Manhattan, the acceptance rate was set at the default value of pyABC's MedianEpsilon function, an error criterion of 0.001 was used, and the maximum number of generations equals 5.

2.3.2. Data availability

To illustrate the methodology, we selected swIAV as a case study, given its relevance to both animal health and potential zoonotic transmission. Although recent evidence suggests that swIAV more commonly circulates endemically among weaned pigs and sows, finishing pigs remain of interest due to their role in production efficiency and the economic impact of swIAV-related growth impairment. For this study, the full farrow-to-finish farm was simulated. To illustrate detailed “pen-level” data availability, we highlighted the fattening area, which was subdivided into pens. Fig. 3 shows the pen layout in the fattening area, chosen for its relatively uniform housing conditions. Dashed arrows indicate potential transmission between neighboring pens. While all production areas in principle can be subdivided into pens, we used the fattening area as an example because its housing structure is relatively simple and therefore well suited for demonstrating the framework. This emphasis was motivated not only by the zoonotic potential of swIAV, but also by the practical advantages of modeling disease dynamics in this phase. Other production areas were treated as mixed populations, from which only aggregated infection data could be obtained.

HogDSim is a general farrow-to-finish farm framework that simulates all production areas, transfers, and movement routines. For calibration and demonstration, we did not restrict the simulation itself but instead varied which outputs were treated as the synthetic “observed” data. Depending on the scenario, these ranged from pen-level infection status in the fattening area, to aggregated infection counts across age groups, to full-farm infection records (see Section 2.3.3). This design allowed us to contrast detailed observations with more limited, aggregated data, thereby representing a spectrum of constrained-surveillance settings while retaining the full ecological interactions of the farm.

Transmission through the movement of farmers is based on the connection and times spent in different areas (see Section 2.1.3). To quantify this input, we used the data from an internal monitoring system that employs detection points located in various production areas within the farm. Farmers wear personal Bluetooth® beacons that transmit signals to these detection points when entering and staying in a production area. This technology has been developed by Animal Data Analytics (ADA) under the name Biorisk® [6]. This system enables high-resolution mapping of the farmer's movement, which can be used to calculate the time spent in each production area and quantify the potential for indirect pathogen transmission due to farmer movement between pens or rooms. We used movement data from the Biorisk® system to parameterize the farmer movement transmission component in the Emulsion model. The movement data used include entry timestamps for detection zones. Exit times are not available. This movement data was processed and anonymized for privacy. To approximate duration time in a production area, we computed differences between successive entries as described in Appendix B (see Supplementary material).

All parameters, except the probabilities governing infection from outside the farm, were obtained from the literature (Table 1). Synthetic infection data were generated using the following transmission rates: $\beta_{int} = 17.01$, $\beta_{ext} = 9.87$, $\beta_{pen} = 9.87$, and $\beta_{aux} = 0.1$. Each of these transmission parameters represents an aggregate pathway, capturing all plausible routes of infection at the corresponding scale, rather than a single isolated mechanism as defined Sections 2.1.3–2.1.6.

In summary, the data used in this swIAV case consist of: (i) synthetic infection outputs from HogDSim (see Section 2.3.3), (ii) farmer movement records from the Biorisk® monitoring system, and (iii) parameter values drawn from the swIAV literature, with transmission parameters specified for calibration. Together, these inputs provide the

empirical and synthetic basis for illustrating and evaluating the ABC-SMC methodology.

The model was executed 100 times with the specified transmission rates to generate candidate synthetic datasets. For each run, infection trajectories were recorded, and the median trajectory across all simulations was calculated. The single run whose output most closely matched this median was then selected as the synthetic dataset for parameter estimation. Fig. 4 presents this trajectory, with the dip at week 17 corresponding to the transition between two fattening batches. The use of synthetic data offers the advantage that the modeler has complete knowledge of the system that generated the data, enabling a clear assessment of both the potential and the limitations of parameter estimation. This advantage reflects the controlled use of synthetic data for calibration and evaluation, while acknowledging that empirical data remain the preferred and most valuable foundation for model development [2,11,34,42].

2.3.3. Calibration using datasets with varying information availability

Using the model, we evaluated four estimation scenarios that differ in the type and resolution of epidemiological data assumed available for calibration. In the swIAV case study, this epidemiological data corresponds to synthetic infection outputs of varying granularity, ranging from coarse pen-level detection to detailed individual-level records. The scenarios, ordered by increasing detail, are:

1. **Total infected fattening pens:** only the number of infected fattening pens (i.e. pens with at least one infected pig) at a given time is available. This reflects common practice for swIAV detection, where pen status is inferred from pooled samples such as chewing ropes.
2. **Aggregate infections per age group:** the total number of infected pigs per age group is available from the other production areas, which are modeled as mixed populations. These counts are aggregated over a specified period. In practice, such data might come from periodic sampling and provide a broader, though temporally coarser, view of farm-level infection than Scenario 1.
3. **Total infected fattening pigs:** weekly counts of infected pigs in the fattening area are available, offering more detailed information than pen-level status alone.
4. **Total infections across all pigs:** weekly infection records for all production stages are available over time. This represents an idealized, highly detailed dataset that is rarely attainable in practice.

2.4. Example application to within-farm biosecurity measures against swine influenza A virus

To demonstrate the practical application of our model in evaluating farm biosecurity protocols, we conducted a case study focusing on measures designed to mitigate the spread of swIAV. This case study builds upon the parameter calibration phase, in which the same disease dynamics were simulated. Because swIAV is transmitted primarily through direct contact, aerosol dispersion, contaminated surfaces, and human interaction, we evaluated three categories of interventions: (i) restrictions on personnel movement within the farm, for example limiting worker access from breeding sow units to the nursery—a high-risk movement since piglets are highly susceptible to swIAV [6]; (ii) controls on animal movement, referring to the routine transfer of pigs between production stages (e.g., removal of exposed or infectious pig before moving from farrowing to nursery, or nursery to fattening); and (iii) closure of auxiliary transmission pathways, as described in Section 2.1.6. While in practice such auxiliary pathways cannot be completely eliminated, in the HogDSim simulations their closure is assumed for simplicity. The individual and combined effects of these measures are summarized in Table 2.

Swine influenza A virus spreads much faster compared to other swine diseases with a direct transmission rate of $\beta_{int} = 17.01$ per week and an

Fig. 3. Pen layout in a fattening compartment. Dashed arrows indicate potential transmission between neighboring pens via direct contact. If indirect pathways (e.g., aerosol exposure) are considered, transmission can occur between any pair of pens.

Fig. 4. Representative infection trajectory across two fattening batches. Infection trajectory from the simulation run that most closely matches the median of 100 runs of the farrow-to-finish model. The decline at week 17 marks the transition between the first and second fattening batches.

indirect transmission rate of $\beta_{ext} = \beta_{pen} = 9.87$ per week based on the airborne transmission rate of Model 2 by Cadore et al. [11]. For the transmission parameter of the auxiliary transmission routes, we used $\beta_{aux} = \beta_{int}/178$, the transmission rate between rooms of swIAV based on Reynolds et al. [42]. Note that the indirect transmission parameter is defined by Cadore et al. [11] as airborne infection in the same room, which matches our assumption for neighboring pen transmission. Since there is no information on transmission through farmer movement, we assume the same parameter value as airborne transmission between neighboring rooms. The time horizon used in the simulation is 170 weeks. Table 1 summarizes the parameters used in the model for this case study.

The present analysis considers two distinct operational frameworks: perfect external biosecurity and imperfect external biosecurity. In a perfect external biosecurity situation, the introduction of an external pathogen is precluded; the infection is already present inside the farm, and virus spread is governed solely by interactions within the farm and biosecurity compliance. In contrast, imperfect external biosecurity allows for the introduction of pathogens at a constant

Table 2

Biosecurity scenarios considered in the swIAV case study. The scenarios represent individual interventions and their combinations, covering farmer movement, animal transfer, and auxiliary transmission routes.

a	Baseline scenario
b	Avoidance of high-risk farmer movement
c	Removing infectious pigs before transfer
d	No risky movement (b) and removal of half of infected pigs before transfer
e	Combination of b and c
f	Removing exposed and infectious pigs during transfer
g	Closing of auxiliary transmission route
h	Combination of b and g
i	Combination of c and g
j	Combination of b, c, and g
k	Combination of b, f, and g

rate, representing external disease incursions from external sources, such as wildlife, contaminated fomites, or visitors. It is important to note that the model does not differentiate between these types of introductions.

Fig. 5. Posterior distributions of the transmission parameters under varying levels of available information. (A) Total infected fattening pens only, (B) aggregate pig infections per age group, (C) total infected fattening pigs per unit time, and (D) total infections for all pigs per unit time. Columns from left to right correspond to β_{int} , β_{aux} , β_{ext} , and β_{pen} ; rows follow the same order from top to bottom. Narrow posterior distributions along the diagonal indicate precision, while proximity to the true value (dashed vertical line) reflects accuracy.

3. Results

3.1. Parametrization and model calibration

This section illustrates the application of the farrow-to-finish model and the ABC-SMC method for estimating the transmission parameters β_{int} , β_{ext} , β_{pen} , and β_{aux} .

Fig. 5 presents kernel density estimation (KDE) matrices of the posterior distributions for these parameters under four data availability scenarios (A-D). Each diagonal panel shows the marginal distribution of a single parameter, while the off-diagonal panels display pairwise relationships. Dashed vertical lines mark the true parameter values used to generate the synthetic data in Fig. 4. Narrower marginal distributions and closer alignment with the dashed lines indicate more accurate and

Fig. 6. Violin plots of the cumulative number of infected pigs with various within-farm and external biosecurity measures under different scenarios (swIAV Case). (A) Perfect external biosecurity with endemic disease ($p_{enc} = p_{inf} = p_{trans} = 0$). Imperfect external biosecurity under different levels of periodic pathogen introduction: (B-D) Imperfect external biosecurity with periodic pathogen introduction at increasing levels: low ($p_{enc} = p_{inf} = p_{trans} = \mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$), medium ($p_{enc} = p_{inf} = p_{trans} = \mathcal{U}[0, 0.5]$), and high ($p_{enc} = p_{inf} = p_{trans} = \mathcal{U}[0, 0.9]$).

precise estimates. In the off-diagonal plots, scatter point aggregation and concentrated bright regions in the heatmaps reflect higher precision, while the overlaid black points denote the true parameter pairs. The proximity of these points to the high-density regions indicates the accuracy of the estimates.

Across scenarios, the precision and accuracy of parameter estimates improve progressively from Fig. 5A to D, as shown by increasingly narrow posterior distributions and better alignment with the true values. The internal transmission parameter within production stages, β_{int} , is consistently the most accurately estimated. The between-pen transmission parameter, β_{pen} , is also well recovered, though its value is underestimated in scenario B (Fig. 5B). The farmer-movement parameter, β_{ext} , falls within the correct interval but shows wider posterior distributions, reflecting lower precision compared to β_{int} and β_{pen} . In contrast, the auxiliary transmission parameter, β_{aux} , is consistently overestimated across all scenarios. Overestimation of β_{aux} reflects its weak identifiability since indirect routes exert minimal influence on epidemic trajectories, allowing diverse β_{aux} values to fit observed patterns. This underscores the need for targeted data before interpreting β_{aux} for decision-making, whereas the inference for β_{int} and β_{pen} remains robust.

3.2. Within-farm biosecurity measures against swine influenza virus

We used the model to assess the effect of several biosecurity practices on the spread of swIAV within a simulated farrow-to-finish pig production system. Fig. 6 summarizes the cumulative number of infected pigs

under different biosecurity measures and external introduction probabilities. Each violin plot represents the distribution of outcomes across repeated simulations, with black dots indicating medians. Note that in Fig. 6B–D represent low, medium, and high probability of pathogen introduction from outside the farm, respectively. For the aforementioned subplots, there are also three violin plots per biosecurity practice, which indicates the different levels of probability success of external biosecurity.

One of the most effective biosecurity measures, as evidenced by Fig. 6, is the removal of both infectious and exposed individuals prior to their movement from one area to another. Furthermore, the elimination of potential disease transmission through auxiliary routes in addition to the biosecurity measures previously mentioned is expected to result in the least number of infected swine. However, implementing this strategy is often impractical due to the difficulty of detecting exposed individuals and completely preventing auxiliary transmission. Among the more feasible measures ((b)–(e) in Fig. 6), limiting risky farmer movements is less effective than the removal of infectious pigs before movement. This conclusion is consistent across all scenarios examined, including those involving varying degrees of external biosecurity effectiveness (see Fig. 6). Moreover, the combination of these measures yields only a modest improvement over the standalone removal of infectious pigs before movement.

In scenarios with imperfect external biosecurity, it is crucial to consider the impact of measures designed to prevent the entry of pathogens from outside the farm. In Fig. 6B–D, we observed that in some cases

Fig. 7. Violin plots of cumulative swIAV infections across five pig population groups under biosecurity measures a-k with $p_{biosec} = 1$. Population groups are farrowers and newborns, weaned piglets, fatteners, non-gestating sows, and gestating sows. Each violin represents the distribution of cumulative infection counts across repeated simulations, with black dots marking the medians.

higher success in preventing external pathogen entry was associated with a marginal increase in the median number of infected individuals within the farm. For instance, under a low probability of external introduction (Fig. 6B) with biosecurity measures (d), (f), and (j), the median infection counts shift slightly upward as external biosecurity success improves. This counterintuitive pattern reflects stochastic variability in the simulations rather than a true negative effect, and the observed differences remain small in magnitude and not statistically significant relative to the other median values under the same measures. More importantly, measure (f) still resulted in one of the lowest number of possible infections overall. Overall, a high probability of external biosecurity success typically leads to a median number of infections that aligns with the lowest possible values. However, some of these exhibit a wider range of outcomes compared to those with low or medium levels of external biosecurity success (see also Fig. 6C and D). Regarding the heightened risk of external disease introduction, it can be seen that biosecurity measure (f) is comparable to k in terms of their effectiveness in reducing the number of infections (see Fig. 6C and D). This indicates that implementing measures in addition to the removal of exposed and infected pigs does not significantly improve the control of swIAV when the potential pathogen introduction from outside sources is medium or high.

In addition to the farm-level findings, Fig. 7 disaggregates the impact of biosecurity measures across five production stages (farrowers/newborns, weaned piglets, fatteners, non-gestating sows, gestating sows). Violin plots show cumulative infections per stage, highlighting how combined interventions (e.g., biosecurity measure k) consistently reduce outbreak size. For farrowers and newborns, the baseline scenario yields a median infection count with wide variability, whereas measures that sequentially add movement restrictions and removal of infectious (I) and exposed (E) pigs (e.g., from b through f) progressively shift the distribution downward and narrow its spread. The most stringent measure (k) produces the lowest median and tightest distribution, indicating a markedly more reliable reduction in outbreak size for this case study. A similar pattern emerges for the fattening stage: intermediate single-focus measures yield modest declines from the baseline me-

dian, but only the combined intervention (k) drives the median down to around 250 with reduced variance. In the high-contact weaned-piglet group, even the robust combination (k) lowers the median from approximately 2000 to about 1200, yet with a broader tail than seen in other groups, underscoring that stochastic transmission dynamics and residual contacts can sustain occasional larger outbreaks despite strict internal controls.

For sows, both non-gestating and gestating stages, the baseline medians are incrementally reduced by measures such as prohibiting risky movements and prior removal of infectious animals (measure (e)). However, the full suite of interventions (k) again achieves the greatest decline and compresses the distribution, signifying enhanced consistency in outbreak prevention. These subgroup-specific results reinforce the earlier farm-wide conclusion that single interventions may yield moderate benefits but are generally insufficient to guarantee low infection counts. For measure (f), it is significantly more effective in reducing infections in the non-gestating, gestating, and fattening stages, but not as effective in other production stages. Consequently, layered biosecurity, such as combining movement controls, removal of both infectious and exposed pigs, and blocking auxiliary transmission routes, emerges as the most effective and reliable strategy to minimize swIAV spread across all production stages in farrow-to-finish systems based on the simulations from HogDSim.

4. Discussion

The hybrid stochastic discrete-time model developed in this study offers a comprehensive framework for investigating disease transmission dynamics within a farrow-to-finish swine farm. This approach integrates the intricate dynamics of an agent-based model with the computational efficiency of a compartmental model, providing a versatile instrument for simulating the propagation of infectious diseases, such as swIAV, within complex farm environments. Although swIAV was used as a case study, the framework is pathogen-agnostic and can be adapted to other infectious diseases of swine or similar production systems. By explicitly modeling individual animals and their interactions, the agent-based

component captures the stochasticity inherent in disease transmission, while the compartmental component facilitates efficient simulation of large populations and long time horizons [11].

Agent-based models often require many parameters [25] and therefore require a lot of data or directly estimated parameters to be parameterized [9]. By comparing four different scenarios in the approximation of the parameters with varying amounts of information, we were able to demonstrate the effect of information availability and evaluate the robustness of the proposed parameter estimation framework with HogDSim.

The parameter estimation results, as illustrated in Fig. 5, robustly demonstrate that the accuracy and precision of the estimates are directly proportional to data availability. The internal transmission parameter within an age group, β_{int} , was the most accurately estimated, followed closely by the transmission parameter between fattening pens, β_{pen} . However, the external transmission parameter, β_{ext} , showed wider posterior distributions, indicating less precision in its estimation. The auxiliary transmission parameter, β_{aux} , was consistently overestimated across all scenarios. This occurs because the auxiliary pathway contributes only marginally to overall transmission dynamics, meaning that a wide range of β_{aux} values can reproduce similar epidemic outcomes. As a result, β_{aux} is weakly identifiable under the available data, and its estimates should be interpreted with caution. Importantly, this limitation does not undermine the robustness of β_{int} and β_{pen} , which remain well estimated across scenarios. This demonstrates that scenarios characterized by limited data can nevertheless estimate transmission parameters at an acceptable level, although the refinement of these estimates may require additional computing power [29]. Furthermore, users of HogDSim should be aware of this limitation and provide extensive uncertainty analyses for the least precise parameters.

The granularity of data plays a crucial role in parameter estimation. High-resolution data, such as the infection status of individual pigs, interactions, and movements, will significantly enhance the precision of parameter estimates [23]. Investments in detailed data collection and monitoring systems can yield substantial benefits in disease modeling and control. However, it is imperative to strike a balance between the volume of data collected and the requisite precision and accuracy, given the substantial financial investment involved in both data collection and computing power. If this balance, for instance, in a research project, is infeasible, a collaboration between a data-focused and a modeling-focused project might solve this issue. Additionally, the robustness of HogDSim in estimating β_{int} and β_{pen} across different scenarios indicates that these parameters are less sensitive to variations in data quality and granularity. This robustness is advantageous for practical applications because it can withstand variations in data quality and, to some extent, limited availability [51]. However, it relies on the availability of farmer movement data.

The outcomes of the simulation demonstrate the potential applicability of HogDSim to evaluate biosecurity measures, contingent upon the availability of detailed information on farmer mobility. This is consistent with findings from Alarcón et al. [1], who emphasized that internal biosecurity, particularly the control of personnel and animal movements within farms, is critical for reducing disease transmission. Although many models focus on between-farm dynamics [14,18,24,31], the importance of within-farm movement patterns is increasingly recognized, especially in systems where segregated housing and routine human-animal interactions are common [6,16].

Our case study on swine flu revealed that the removal of both infectious and exposed individuals before their movement is one of the most effective biosecurity measures. This strategy significantly reduces the number of infected swine, as shown in Fig. 6, though its practical implementation is challenging due to the difficulty in detecting exposed individuals before they become infectious. An alternative to this measure would be to quarantine any pigs that may have been exposed before they can be moved to the appropriate stage [3,5]. In addition to the aforementioned measures, completely blocking auxiliary transmission routes

such as indirect contact via equipment or personnel will also reduce infection, a strategy supported by broader reviews of internal biosecurity practices [1].

The effectiveness of removing infectious and exposed individuals depends on the ability to accurately identify these individuals. Advancements in detection technologies, such as rapid diagnostic tests and real-time monitoring systems, can enhance the feasibility and effectiveness of this biosecurity measure [22,47]. Furthermore, the role of human behavior, particularly farmer movements, is critical in disease transmission [10]. However, as shown by our case study, restricting farmer movements cannot always control diseases, when auxiliary pathways are present. Training and awareness programs for farmers on biosecurity practices can complement technological measures and improve overall disease control.

Furthermore, the swIAV case study demonstrates that avoiding risky movement alone is ineffective in controlling the transmission of swine flu. This is similar to the results of Etbaigha et al. [20]. In their transmission model, the transmission rates between areas were modeled as constant. However, HogDSim also indicates that the implementation of additional biosecurity measures in conjunction with the strategic avoidance of high-risk movements, such as the removal of infected individuals, the control of auxiliary routes or vaccination (e.g. [42]), is required to control of swIAV transmission. The difficulty of preventing swIAV transmission might be attributed to the rapid transmission of swIAV and its multiple transmission pathways [20]. Avoiding risky movements may be more effective for diseases with slower transmission rates or pathogens whose spread depends on fomites, thus neglecting this measure is not advisable [6]. Furthermore, given that the farmer movement data utilized in this study is derived from actual movement data in a swine farm, it is possible that risky movements may have been preemptively avoided and inherently embedded within the data.

While HogDSim provides valuable insights on within-farm disease spread, it is also important to point out its limitations. The higher variability in estimating β_{ext} and the consistent overestimation of β_{aux} highlight the need for more granular data on farmer movements, auxiliary contacts, and infection pathways. Future research should focus on collecting detailed empirical data to refine these estimates. Additionally, while useful for validation, the model's reliance on synthetic data for parameter estimation may not fully capture the complexities of real-world disease dynamics. Thus, applying the model to actual epidemiological data will be crucial for further validation and refinement.

In conclusion, this study presents a novel modeling framework that incorporates detailed farmer movement data together with routine animal transfers between production stages in a farrow-to-finish system, allowing for the investigation of disease transmission within the farm in a more detailed manner. In particular, the model offers a powerful tool for evaluating biosecurity measures and informing disease control strategies. Future work should aim to integrate more empirical and real-life data such as disease prevalence or incidence information. Furthermore, the application of the HogDSim framework should be explored in the context of other infectious diseases and various farm settings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jerrold M. Tubay: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization; **Egil A.J. Fischer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Marina Meester:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology; **Tijs Tobias:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Funding acquisition; **Arjan Stegeman:** Writing – review

& editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Code availability

The codes used for the model, simulation, and parameter estimation in this study are available via [the HogDSim GitHub Repository](#).

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used Microsoft Copilot in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Ethical statement

This study does not involve any experiments on humans or animals, and no ethical approval was required. Therefore, an ethical statement is not applicable.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Jerrold M. Tubay reports employment with the University of the Philippines Los Baños, where he was on leave without pay from 1 July 2023 to 30 June 2025. His resignation from UPLB took effect on 1 July 2025. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary material

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